

EDGAR SCHEIN'S MODEL OF ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE LEVELS AS A HOLOGRAM

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(a scientific article)

Summary:

The current study dwells upon Edgar Schein's original framework for exploring organizational culture by classifying its elements to three levels. Important directions of model's elaboration are identified and analyzed. The last have been undertaken by different researchers in the last three decades, based on individual's necessities, involvement and experience with the application in practice of this model. Viewing Schein's model as a hologram is recommended as a way to dissolve subjectively identified by different authors issues or ambiguities in this framework. Thus, a contemporary, useful and richer "snapshot" of this model is proposed for use in the organizations during these turbulent times when cultural intelligence capabilities come of greater importance for their successful market performance.

JEL: M14; L20; D03

Full-text:

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Cite it this way:

1. Dimitrov, K., (2013) "Edgar Schein's model of organizational culture levels as a hologram", (a study), Economic studies journal, Bulgarian Academy of

Sciences, issue 4, pp3-36; ISSN 0205-3292, available at:

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